
Effect of Heat on some Properties of Normal and Pozzolanic Concrete

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Abstract

Reinforced concrete structures are sometimes subjected to astronomically high temperatures especially when gutted by fire. This research is aimed at finding the effect of heat on normal and pozzolanic concrete. This study includes the investigation of the properties of normal and pozzolanic concrete. Laboratory tests carried out are sieve analysis, slump, specific gravity, water absorption, and compressive strength. The results of sieve analysis reveal that the coefficients of uniformity (Cu) and curvature (Cc) for river sand are 2.25 and 1.00, respectively, while those for granite are 1.64 and 1.14. Slump test results indicate that the values for both normal and pozzolanic concrete vary from 57 to 60 mm, indicating medium workability. Specific gravity test results show values of 2.59 for river sand, 2.12 for rice husk ash, and 2.63 for granite. Water absorption values vary from 1.14 to 5.25% for normal concrete cubes, 1.83 to 5.89% for pozzolanic concrete cubes, and 4.11 to 8.16 % for normal and pozzolanic sandcrete blocks. The compressive strength of normal concrete cubes varies from 17.10 to 25.90 N/mm², while the values for pozzolanic concrete cubes vary from 17.00 to 26.90 N/mm². The compressive strength of Sandcrete blocks have range from 1.74 to 2.39 N/mm². The cubes and blocks produced satisfy the strength minimum requirements stated in Nigerian Industrial and International British Standards. The normal and pozzolanic concrete compressive strength reduced by 21.3 and 27.5 % respectively when subjected to temperature of 500^oC at 56 days of curing. Statistical t-test, at 5 % significance level, shows that there is no significant difference between the strength of normal and pozzolanic concrete samples subjected to temperature of 500^oC. The study discovers that temperatures greater than 400^oC can significantly weaken strength of concrete. It is recommended that concrete should not be subjected to temperatures beyond 400 degrees Celsius.

Keywords: Concrete, Strength, Heat, and Effect

Introduction

According to Manasseh (2010), concrete is a blend of cement, fine and coarse aggregates, and water, combined in specific proportions to achieve desired strength. The chemical reaction between cement and water produces a paste that acts as a binding agent, bonding the aggregate particles together. Over time, the mixture hardens, forming a solid material that is highly resistant to compression but weak when subjected to tension.

Concrete typically comprises cement, water, aggregates, and sometimes admixtures. Admixtures are occasionally incorporated to modify specific properties of concrete. Concrete is defined as a composite material composed primarily of a binding medium, which contains embedded particles or fragments of inert material filler, as explained by Gahlot and Sanjay (2006). The binder consists of a mixture of Cement and water, while the filler can be sourced from a diverse variety of natural or artificial aggregates. The strength properties of hardened concrete encompass shear strength, compressive strength, static modulus of elasticity, split tensile strength, shear stress, water absorption, flexural strength, and shear modulus (Osadebe, 2003). These properties are significantly influenced by the proportions of its constituent materials. The characteristics of concrete are heavily influenced by the type and properties of the constituent materials, the mixing method employed, the proportions of each component, the processes of transportation, placement, finishing, and curing, as well as the presence of entrained air, impurities, admixtures, and the age of concrete (Neville, 2003).

Sandcrete hollow block is one of the common building materials used in most building constructions that require walling units, in many countries of the world; Nigeria inclusive. Sandcrete hollow block is made from the mixture of cement, sand (fine aggregate) and water in a standard specified mix proportion. It has the following nominal standard sizes of: 450 x 230 x 100mm, 450 x 230 x 150mm, and 450 x 230 x 230mm (NIS 87: 2006).

British Standard (BS EN 77-3) (2006), defines block as a masonry unit of larger size in all dimensions than specified for bricks but no dimension should exceed 650mm nor should the height exceed either its length or six times its thickness. Concrete block strength varies from 3.45 to 1.70 N/mm² (BS EN 77-3:2006 and The Federal Ministry of Works:1979).

Concrete is a widely used construction material known for its strength, durability, and versatility. It is employed in construction of buildings, bridges, roads, etcetera. However, like any other material, concrete is also susceptible to the influence of external factors, including high temperature. Heat can have significant negative effect on concrete, both during its initial curing process and when it is exposed to high temperatures afterward (Morsy *et al.*, 2010).

Elevated temperatures are widely recognized as a significant threat to the integrity of concrete, causing substantial damage to its micro and macro-structures. This degradation could lead to a broad deterioration in the mechanical properties of concrete, with potential repercussions at the structural level; Particularly in the event of fire. Such high temperatures could cause concrete to spall, exposing reinforcing bars to flames. When subjected to heightened temperatures, concrete undergoes notable physicochemical transformations. The response of concrete structural elements to fire hinges on the interplay of their thermal, mechanical, and deformation characteristics (Anupama *et al.*, 2019).

Exposure to heightened temperatures has a marked impact on both the physical and mechanical attributes of concrete. Fire stands as one of the natural perils that pose a threat to building constructions. Elevated temperatures result in progressive breakdown of cement gel

structure, reduced durability, heightened propensity for drying shrinkage, structural cracks, and even changes in aggregate color (Anupama *et al.*, 2019).

The foremost effects of heightened temperatures on concrete include the dehydration of cement paste, elevated porosity, shifts in moisture content, thermal expansion, changes in pore pressure, loss of strength, thermal cracking due to incompatibility, thermal creep, and the risk of thermal spalling owing to excessive pore pressure. The distribution and movement of water, whether in liquid or vapour form, play a pivotal role in causing localized damage to concrete structures. As concrete heats, the endothermic nature of vaporization induces steep thermal gradients and high vapour pressures, which can lead to tensile stresses surpassing the concrete's strength (Noumowe and Debicki, 2002). Studies on heat-exposed concrete have shown that reinforced concrete structures tend to perform well in fires due to inherent qualities of cement-based materials, such as fire resistance and low thermal diffusivity. This latter attribute allows the outer heat-damaged layers to shield the inner core from excessively high temperatures, even during extended fire exposure. Conversely, the mechanical properties of concrete are markedly affected by elevated temperatures (Kodur, 2014).

The properties of High Strength Concrete (HSC) react differently to temperature fluctuations compared to those of Normal Strength Concrete (NSC). This variance is particularly pronounced in mechanical properties, which are influenced by factors such as strength, moisture content, density, heating rate, presence of silica fume, and porosity (Kodur, 2014). Concrete structures when exposed to fire conditions vary depending on factors like the nature of the fire, the type of loading system, and the specific structure. Failures can arise from diverse reasons, including reductions in bending or tensile strength, diminished shear or torsional strength, and decreased compressive strength, among others (Bikhiet *et al.*, 2014). Understanding the impact of heat on concrete is crucial for ensuring the long-term performance and safety of concrete structures, especially in environments where high temperatures are prevalent or in situations where fire incidents may occur.

According to ASTM C618-78 (2023), pozzolanas are siliceous and aluminous materials that possess limited or no inherent cementing properties. However, when finely divided and combined with water, they react with calcium hydroxide at normal temperatures to form a compound with cementing properties. The reaction that occurs during the mixture of pozzolana and Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) reduces the porosity of the paste and improves the impermeability of concrete (Neville, 2003). Optimum proportions of this mixture also enhance the qualities of fresh and hardened concrete. Gupta (2013), using pozzolana as a partial replacement for cement in concrete production, offers several benefits, including increased resistance to sulfate attack, improved workability, enhanced resistance to alkali-silica reactivity, higher ultimate strength, reduced bleeding, increased durability, and reduced shrinkage. Some common examples of pozzolanic materials include rice husk ash, blast furnace slag, and fly ash.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study investigates the effect of heat on properties of normal and pozzolanic concrete. The specific objectives are to:

- i. determine the grading and specific gravity of the aggregates
- ii. determine the slump of the normal and pozzolanic concrete
- iii. determine the water absorption of normal and pozzolanic concrete
- iv. determine the compressive strength of concrete and blocks produced

Statement of the Problem

Concrete is a composite material made up of aggregates, cement and water. It possesses low thermal conductivity and is non-combustible, hence it is generally considered as a fireproof material. Nevertheless, when used to construct reinforced structures, it is expected to satisfy strength requirement as well as heat resistant requirements. Exposure of concrete to high temperatures reduces its mechanical and physical properties (Naus, 2010). Heat induced dimensional changes, loss of structural integrity, and release of moisture and gases resulting from migration of free water which could adversely affect the intended life of a concrete structure. Therefore, understanding the effect of heat on properties of normal and pozzolanic concrete is essential for reliable design evaluations and assessments.

Materials and Method

The materials used for the study includes Cement, Granite, Sand, Rice Husk Ash and Water.
Cement:

- i. Bua Cement of 43 grade: NIS 444-1: 2018-CEM II/A-L, was used. It was obtained in Makurdi, Nigeria.
- ii. Aggregate used includes river sand, obtained from River Benue and granite. They were obtained in Makurdi, Nigeria. They were prepared to conform with BS 8110-1 (1997) recommendations for structural concrete. The granite has maximum size of 20 mm.
- iii. Rice Husk was burnt for approximately 48 hours in an open air and uncontrolled burning process. The ash collected was sieved through BS standard sieve size 75µm. Batching was done by volume at replacement of Cement by 15% RHA.
- iv. The water used for the concrete was pipe-borne water obtained at the Civil Engineering Laboratory, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, Nigeria.

Grading of aggregates:

Grading tests were performed on the river sand and granite to the methods described in BS EN 933-1 (1997) and BS 812-103 (1990).

Water absorption test:

The water absorption tests of the aggregates were carried out according to the method described in BS EN 1097-6 (2013). The water absorption of the aggregate was calculated using equation (1).

$$\text{Water Absorption} = \frac{(\text{Weight of Oven - Dry Sample} - \text{Weight of SSD Sample})}{\text{Weight of SSD Sample}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Specific gravity test:

The specific gravity test was carried out on the aggregates as described in BS EN 1097-6 (2013). The specific gravity was calculated using equation 2.

$$G_s = \frac{M_2 - M_1}{(M_4 - M_1) - (M_3 - M_2)} \quad (2)$$

G_s = specific gravity

M_1 = weight of empty flask (g)

M_2 = weight of empty flask + weight of the sample (g)

M_3 = weight of empty flask + weight of the sample + water (g)

M_4 = weight of empty flask + water (g)

Preparation of the concrete:

Concrete grades 20 N/mm² was designed for (Appendix G) using a constant free water to cement ratio of 0.58, as prescribed in BS 1881-116 (1983). Mixing was done manually. Concrete was cast in cubes and fully compacted to expel entrapped air. Concrete was placed

in three layers and compaction was made at each layer of placement. Twenty (20) concrete cubes, of side 150mm were cast. The Pozzolanic Concrete was made from 15 % Rice Husk Ash and Cement. A mix ratio of 1:5 was used for the sandcrete blocks. Twenty (20) sandcrete blocks were produced. The cubes were cured for 28 and 56 days while the blocks were cured for 28 days prior to testing.

Slump test:

The workability of the concrete was determined through slump test. Slump test was conducted as described in BS EN 12350: Part 2 (2000).

Compression test:

The compression test was conducted as specified in BS EN 12390-3 (2009). The compressive strength is given by equation 3.

$$\text{Compressive Strength } (\sigma \text{ in N/mm}^2) = \frac{\text{crushing load of cube (N)}}{\text{Area of cubes (mm}^2)} \quad (3)$$

Heat Test

Heating of concrete and sandcrete blocks to specific temperatures for a defined duration was conducted in controlled laboratory conditions to study their behavior under high temperatures. Concrete cubes and sandcrete blocks were used for the study, and a furnace capable of reaching and maintaining temperatures above 500°C was used. A timer was used to monitor the duration of heating. The samples were carefully placed into furnace using tongs and heat-resistant gloves, and the timer was set for 2 hours. The Concrete samples were heated for 2 hours at the specified temperatures of 100°C, 200°C, 300°C, 400°C, and 500°C. Then, they were carefully removed and placed in a well-ventilated area, to allow them to cool to room temperature. The blocks were then subjected to compression.

Results and Discussion

Specific Gravity

Table 2 shows the Results of specific gravity for the river sand, rice husk ash and granite. The average specific gravity for the river sand, rice husk ash and granite are 2.59, 2.12 and 2.63 respectively.

Table 1: Results of Specific Gravity Tests of the River Sand, Rice Husk Ash and Granite

Description	River sand		Rice Husk Ash		Granite	
	Test 1	Test 2	Test 1	Test 2	Test 1	Test 2
Mass of flask + sample + water (M_3) g	110.50	111.20	108.00	89.20	112.00	111.00
Mass of flask + sample (M_2) g	37.20	38.50	44.50	44.00	45.00	44.50
Mass of flask + water (M_4) g	104.24	104.11	82.30	80.20	100.90	100.30
Mass of flask (M_1) g	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00	27.00
$(M_2 - M_1)$ g	10.20	11.50	17.50	17.00	18.00	17.50
$(M_4 - M_1)$ g	77.24	77.11	55.30	53.20	73.90	73.30
$(M_3 - M_2)$ g	73.30	72.70	63.50	45.20	67.00	66.50
$[(M_4 - M_1) - (M_3 - M_2)]$ g	3.94	4.41	8.20	8.00	6.90	6.80
$G_s = \frac{M_2 - M_1}{(M_4 - M_1) - (M_3 - M_2)}$	2.59	2.58	2.10	2.13	2.61	2.64
Average Specific Gravity	2.59		2.12		2.63	

Figures 1 and 2 show the results of sieve analysis for the river sand and granite respectively. It was observed that coefficient of uniformity (Cu) and coefficient of curvature (Cc) of the river sand are 2.25 and 1.00 respectively. The coefficient of uniformity (Cu) and coefficient of curvature (Cc) of the granite are 1.64 and 1.14 respectively. The coefficient of uniformity (Cu) and coefficient of curvature (Cc) of the granite are 1.64 and 1.14 respectively. These values agree with the findings of Obam *et al.* (2024).

Figure 1: Grading Curve for the River Sand

Figure 2: Grading Curve for the River Sand

Figure 3 shows the results of slump test values for normal and pozzolanic concretes respectively. The values for the normal and pozzolanic concrete are 57 and 60 mm respectively. The slump values vary from 50 to 100 mm; which indicates a medium workability as reported by Neville (2011). The workability class is S1, as stated in BS EN 206 (2013). Similar Results were obtained by Gupta, Y.O. (2013).

Figure 3: Slump Values for the Normal and Pozzolanic Concrete

Figures 4 to 6 show the water absorption of normal and pozzolanic concrete cubes and sandcrete blocks. The water absorption of the normal cubes varies from 1.14 to 5.25 %. The values for pozzolanic concrete cubes vary from 1.83 to 5.89 %. Water absorption of both the normal and pozzolanic sandcrete blocks vary from 1.83 to 5.89 % respectively. Water absorption increases with temperature rise for both normal and pozzolanic sandcrete blocks. Pozzolanic blocks consistently show higher water absorption than normal sandcrete blocks at all temperatures. Majority of the samples have water absorption below than the limit of 5% specified for normal concrete (Nadir and Sujatha, 2018).

Figure 4: Water Absorption Test Results for the Normal and Pozzolanic Concrete at 28-day

Figure 5: Water Absorption Test Results for the Normal and Pozzolanic Concrete at 56-day

Figure 6: Water Absorption Test Results for the Sandcrete Blocks at 28-day

Figures 7 to 9 show values of compressive strength of the normal and pozzolanic concrete and sandcrete blocks. The compressive strength of the normal concrete varies from 17.10 to 25.90 N/mm². Strength values for the pozzolanic concrete vary from 17.00 to 26.90 N/mm² while the compressive strength of both the normal and pozzolanic sandcrete blocks varies from 1.74 to 2.39 N/mm². The compressive strength of normal concrete varies from 17.10 to 25.90 N/mm². The strength of pozzolanic concrete cubes varies from 17.00 to 26.90 N/mm². The strength of both normal and pozzolanic sandcrete blocks varies from 1.74 to 2.39 N/mm² respectively. The results obtained conform with the findings of Obam *et al.* (2024) and Ubi *et al.* (2022). These findings are in line with BS 8810 (1985), which states that the minimum compressive strength required for concrete to be used for structural purpose at 28-day should be 20 N/mm² and above. The strength of sandcrete blocks falls within the

specifications of NBRRI (2006), which recommend a minimum compressive strength of sandcrete hollow blocks to be within the range of 2.5 to 3.45N/mm². This is inline with the minimum requirement reported by the Nigerian Industrial Standard (NIS 87,2000). The sandcrete blocks also meet the requirements of the Nigerian Building Code (2006), which specifies a minimum strength of 1.7N/mm².

From the results obtained, the normal concrete strength is higher than the pozzolanic concrete strength at 28-day while the pozzolanic concrete strength is observed to be higher than the normal concrete at 56-day. The higher compressive strength of normal concrete at 28-day could be attributed to the faster hydration rate of Portland cement compared to pozzolanic materials. Normal concrete primarily relies on the hydration of cement, which leads to early formation of calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gel, responsible for its early strength gain. In contrast, pozzolanic concrete contains rice husk ash (RHA), which react more slowly with calcium hydroxide (CH) from the cement hydration. These pozzolanic reactions are slow, resulting in lower early-age strength. However, at 56-day, the pozzolanic concrete exhibited superior compressive strength compared to normal concrete. This increase is due to the long-term pozzolanic reaction between the RHA and the calcium hydroxide produced by cement hydration. Over time, these reactions generate additional C-S-H, which increases the strength and durability of the concrete. As the RHA continues to react, they fill voids and refine the pore structure of the concrete, contributing to a denser matrix and improved strength performance at later ages. The result is in line with Al-Jumaily *et al.* (2015); they observed that pozzolanic concrete of fly ash exhibited lower early strength at 28-day compared to normal concrete.

Figure 7: Compressive Strength Test Results for the Normal and Pozzolanic Concrete at 28-day

Figure 8: Compressive Strength Test Results for the Normal and Pozzolanic Concrete at 56-day

Figure 9: Compressive Strength Test Results for the Sandcrete Blocks at 28-day

Figure 10 shows the percentage reduction in strength at temperature of 500 °C. The compressive strength of normal concrete cubes, pozzolanic concrete cubes, and sandcrete blocks decrease with temperature rise. The Pozzolanic concrete cubes have lower strength than conventional cubes at all temperatures, however, both types of the concrete cubes exhibit decline in compressive strength as temperature rises. As temperature increases, the compressive strength of pozzolanic and normal sandcrete blocks decreases (Ukpata *et al.* 2022). The significant decrease in compressive strength at elevated temperatures highlights the potential degradation of concrete structure when exposed to prolonged high thermal conditions.

Figure 10: Percentage Reduction in Strength at Temperature of 500 °C Vs Concrete Sample

Conclusion

Concrete, like many other materials, can be destroyed by severe heat. This study subjected both normal and pozzolanic concrete to various degrees of temperature in a furnace. Some tests of the physical and mechanical properties of the concrete and its materials were carried out. The following results are obtained:

- i. The sieve analysis reveals that the river sand has coefficients of uniformity (Cu) and curvature (Cc) of 2.25 and 1.00, respectively, while granite has values of 1.64 Cu and 1.14 Cc.
- ii. Specific gravity tests show values of 2.60 for river sand, 2.12 for RHA, and 2.59 for granite respectively.
- iii. The slump test Results for both normal and pozzolanic concrete varies from 57 to 60 mm, indicating medium workability.
- iv. Water absorption tests indicate that normal concrete cubes have absorption rates between 1.14 % and 5.25 %, while pozzolanic concrete cubes have values that vary from 1.83% to 5.89 %. Both normal and pozzolanic sandcrete blocks showed similar absorption rates varies from 4.11 to 8.16 %.
- v. Density tests reveal that normal concrete cubes have densities between 2504 to 2686 kg/m³, pozzolanic concrete cubes have values that vary from 2502 to 2601 kg/m³, and sandcrete blocks have densities between 1860 and 2173 kg/m³.
- vi. The compressive strength of normal concrete cubes varies from 17.10 to 25.90 N/mm², while pozzolanic concrete cubes have strengths between 17.00 and 26.90 N/mm². Compressive strength of Sandcrete blocks varies from 1.74 to 2.39 N/mm².

- vii. The normal and pozzolanic concrete compressive strength were reduced by 21.3 and 27.5 % respectively when subjected to temperature of 500^oC at 56 days of curing. The study discovers that temperatures greater than 400 ^oC can significantly weaken strength of the concrete.

Recommendations

Based on the Results obtained, we recommend are follows:

- i. Concrete should not be exposed to heat beyond 400^oC.
- ii. Due to the adverse effect of heat on concrete, it is advised to design concrete structures that can withstand it.

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